

Brown planthopper (BPH) dispersal range under natural conditions in the Philippines

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Methods for measuring the movement of insect pests frequently require manipulating the insects in ways that may bias results. A fortuitous natural experiment in 1981-83 permitted a quantitative estimate of the dispersal range of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* that avoided this difficulty.

As part of a larger study of the regional dynamics of rice-feeding insects, small kerosene light traps were established across a 17,000-ha area of irrigated, double-cropped rice in Nueva Ecija Province, Philippines. In early Feb 1982, large catches of BPH were noticed in the traps. The numbers caught declined from west to east.

At that time of year, many fields were still being prepared for the dry season crop or had been planted no more than 2 wk earlier. The only possible source of insects was an area of abandoned ricefields along the Chico River, dominated by volunteer rice and *Leersia hexandra*. (Farmers had cultivated the poorly drained area during a time when irrigation had been cut off for canal maintenance.)

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between catches 6-25 Feb and distance from the old ricefields for the 16 sites in the northern half of the study area. An exponential decay fits the data well ($r = -0.92$, $P < 0.001$).

After correcting for the possible immigration from other sources of the 2.5 BPH/trap (estimated from the catch over the 20 d prior to 6 Feb) in the two traps farthest from the old fields, and after integrating and rotating the curve about the origin, I calculated that 50% of dispersing BPH would move less than 2.3 km, 80% less than 4.1 km, and 95% less than 6.5 km.

These estimates assume that dispersal is similar in all directions, which at first seems unlikely. Fifteen of the 16 light trap sites lay between north-northeast and

east of the old fields. To reach them, BPH would have had to fly directly into the prevailing winds (at that time, north-east to east between dusk and dawn).

Catches at the one site that lay downwind of the old fields (circled points in Fig. 1) however, were not notably higher than expected on the basis of the overall regression.

Could BPH have flown such considerable distances upwind? One possibility is that insects were avoiding take-off in strong winds, and that they made repeated flights, particularly near dawn when winds were lighter. These behaviors are known from the literature. Figure 2 supports this interpretation: the median catch in the 6-25 Feb period is seen to occur later in the sites farthest from the old ricefields ($r_s = 0.47$, $P < 0.05$). Note that at the downwind site, the median is reached 2 d later than the closer sites, suggesting that BPH may take more than one night to reach points only a few km away, whether upwind or downwind. ■

1. BPH catches in light traps over the period 6-25 Feb 1982 in relation to distance from Laon, an old-field area. $\ln Y = 9.939 - 0.7340 x$, $n = 32$ traps. Circled data = downwind locations.

2. Date of median catch in the 6-25 Feb period in relation to distance from Laon, an old-field area. $n = 14$ sites.

Integrated pest management-weeds

Ricefield weeds in Chitwan Valley, Nepal

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Rice is the main crop in Chitwan Valley in the central inner Terai of Nepal, about 145 km south of Kathmandu. We surveyed the weeds in transplanted ricefields and determined their dominance Aug-Sep 1987-88.

Fifty weeds were identified (see table). On the basis of Sculthop's life-form categories, the weed flora was composed of 49 emergent weeds and one floating-

Scientific name and summed dominance ratio (SDR) of weeds^a in transplanted ricefields, Chitwan Valley, Nepal.

Scientific name	SDR value ^b
<i>Eleocharis atropurpurea</i> (Retz.) Presl	12.577
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	10.534
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	7.958
<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	7.207
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	6.802
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	5.934
<i>Rotala indica</i> (Willd.) Koehne	4.770
<i>Sagittaria guayanensis</i> Kunth ^a	3.398
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem & Schult.	3.220
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	3.098
<i>Scirpus lateriflorus</i> Gmel.	2.705
<i>Caesulia axillaris</i> Roxb.	2.668
<i>Eriocaulon cinereum</i> R. Br.	2.697
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	2.482
<i>Commelina paludosa</i> B1.	1.718
<i>Cyanotis cristata</i> D. Don	1.705
<i>Ageratum houstonianum</i> Mill.	1.618
<i>Hedyotis diffusa</i> L.	1.528
<i>Ceratopteris thalictroides</i> (L.) Brogn.	1.337
<i>Tenagocharis latifolia</i> (D. Don) Buch.	1.280
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	1.242
<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	1.072
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	0.968
<i>Cyperus squarrosus</i> L.	0.795
<i>Cyperus compressus</i> L.	0.750
<i>Lindernia procumbens</i> (Krock.) Philcox	0.735
<i>Lindernia anagallis</i> (Burm. f.) Pennell	0.724
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i> (L.) Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	0.662
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.) Brenan	0.631
<i>Lindernia ciliata</i> (Colsm.) Pennell	0.571
<i>Amisophacelus axillaris</i> Rolla Rao & Kamathy	0.534
<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i> Webster	0.467
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i> Roxb.	0.448
<i>Melochia concatenata</i> L.	0.434

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Table continued.

Scientific name	SDR value ^b	Scientific name	SDR value ^b
<i>Cyperus haspan</i> L.	0.422	<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	0.185
<i>Hemarthria compressa</i> (L. f.) R. Br.	0.398	<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	0.151
<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> Forst. f.	0.378	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	0.132
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	0.336	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	0.112
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	0.314	<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	0.112
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	0.228	<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	0.112
<i>Eragrostis unioides</i> (Retz.) Nees ex Steud.	0.218	<i>Brachiaria murica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	0.092
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koel	0.197	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i> L.	0.069

^aFloating leaf species. ^bMean ratio of relative density and relative frequency.

leaf weed. *Eriocaulon cinereum* showed a submerged life form in early rice growth stages.

For each species, we determined the summed dominance ratio (SDR)—the average of relative density plus relative

frequency. Seven locations were selected randomly and 10 quadrats in each location were temporarily positioned. Species were counted in 70 one-m² quadrats. On the basis of higher SDR value, *Eleocharis atropurpurea*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala indica*, *Sagittaria guayanensis*, *Alternanthera sessilis*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica* were the most commonly occurring weeds. ■

Water management

Irrigation methods for rice in tropical Australia

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Water is the largest single cost for irrigated dry seeded rice production in north Queensland, Australia. It accounts for about 40% of all variable costs. We evaluated increasing water-use efficiency by

- reducing water use while maintaining grain yield,
- increasing grain yield, while maintaining water use.

The experiment was conducted at Millaroo Research Station (19° 30' S, 147° 30' E) in 1989 dry season (winter). Traditional, intermittent irrigation to the 3-leaf stage, followed by permanent flood

(PF-3L), flooding at sowing (PF-S), flooding at panicle initiation (PF-PI), saturated soil culture (SSC), and intermittent irrigation (II) were compared. SSC is a technique recently developed for soybean: plants are grown on 1.5-m raised beds with water maintained in the furrows between beds, some 10-15 cm below the bed surface. II plots were irrigated by raising the water table to the surface at 7-d intervals. Irrigation treatments were in 288-m² plots replicated three times. Rice cultivar Lemont was used.

Rice yields were 8-9 t/ha in all treatments except II, which yielded 5.4 t/ha (see table). PF-PI and SSC did not reduce grain yield significantly. However, water use of PF-PI (12.1 million liters/ha and SSC (9.4 million liters/ha) was significantly less (P < 0.01) than that of PF-3L (13.7 million liters/ha). Most importantly, water-use efficiency (grain yield per unit consumption of water) of SSC (0.84 t/million liters) was significantly higher than that of PF-3L (0.65 t/million liters).

Grain yield and water use of rice cultivar Lemont grown under 5 irrigation methods at Millaroo Research Station, North Queensland, 1989 dry season.^a

Irrigation treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use ^b (million liters/ha)	Water-use efficiency (t/million liters)	% water ^c saved
Flooding at sowing	9.3 a	14.0 a	0.66 b	0
Intermittent irrigation followed by permanent flood	8.8 ab	13.7 a	0.65 b	
Flooding at panicle initiation	8.4 ab	12.1 b	0.69 ab	12
Saturated soil culture	7.9 b	9.4 c	0.84 a	31
Intermittent irrigation	5.4 c	7.9 d	0.68 ab	42

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bIncludes all irrigation plus rainfall. ^cSavings calculated in relation to PF - 3L.

SSC used up to 1/3 less water than the flooded treatments because evaporation from the saturated soil surface was significantly less than that from a free water surface throughout crop growth. It should be noted that the cultivar used was developed for flooded rice production. The possibility exists that cultivars with improved yield under saturated soil can be developed. ■

Evaluation of drain performance based on head loss fraction in rice-growing acid-saline tract of Kuttanad

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Irrigated rice is the main crop in the acid-saline tract (Kari soils) of Kuttanad in Kerala. Because field elevation (0.5 to 1.5 m below sea level) is much lower than that of the surrounding water bodies, field preparation involves forming a ring bund and draining from inside. Pregerminated seeds are sown into puddled soils both wet and dry seasons.

Soils are extremely acidic and contain toxic concentrations of Fe, Al, and organic products. Yields are very low (1.0-1.5 t/ha), even with 100% adoption of high-yielding varieties. The hydraulic gradient created by the higher elevation water bodies brings toxic salts up to the root zone.

To limit that upward movement of salts and other toxic products, we experimented